

NON-LINEARITY IN EDGE DELAMINATION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE
UNDER COMPRESSION LOADING

H. Chaouk

and

G. P. Steven
Department of Aeronautical Engineering.
The University of Sydney,
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Australia.

ABSTRACT

The fracture behaviour of Graphite/Epoxy composites is of considerable current interest, particularly with regard to their durability and damage tolerance. For this research project reported in this paper an experimental investigation into the fracture mechanisms of certain edge delaminated composites under compression loading has been undertaken. Experimental testing of such laminates produced a non-linear behaviour which has necessitated a change in the analysis procedure for interlaminar fracture in order to determine appropriate fracture parameters.

The specimens tested were of Graphite/Epoxy laminate AS4/3501-6 and contained near surface edge delamination. This delamination is simulated by inserting, during lay-up, a Teflon film at an appropriate location on one side of the specimen near the surface. Testing was performed using a modified Iitri compression jig. An energy release rate criterion was adopted and modified to incorporate the effect of this non-linear behaviour. Non destructive testing was performed during and after loading to acquire accurate information on delamination initiation; this included acoustic emission, dye penetrant X-rays and ultrasonic inspection.

INTRODUCTION

A commonly observed failure mode in laminated composites is delamination between the composite layers. This unique phenomenon is not commonly found in metals. Delamination usually takes the form of separation of plies and is generally initiated at geometric boundaries such as voids, microcracks and foreign inclusions or in some detail design [1] such as a free edge, ply drop-off, co-cured joints or bolted joints. This causes

structural degradation, stiffness reduction and leads ultimately to failure at stresses below the design levels for an undamaged laminate. Therefore understanding of some of the basic delamination behaviour is of great importance in assessing the structural integrity of advanced composite materials and structures. Earlier studies have been reported on this subject which have dealt extensively with the strain energy release rate (G). Some of these studies [2-6] involve tension loaded specimens and linear finite element analysis. Others, have different modes of fracture [7-11] and use the compliance method based on a pure linear relationship. In most of these studies the complexity due to the asymmetry was avoided by creating outer ply delamination on both surfaces and on both edges of specimens, thus being doubly symmetric. Compression testing of delaminated specimens encounters several difficulties [12] and requires a careful and an accurate procedure for data acquisition and result processing. These difficulties are generally associated with the interpretation of the test data which could have considerable scatter and variability due to the various failure modes. Previous work by the authors [3] has shown that some laminates of certain ply configurations experience closure effects where the delaminated portions close inwards under compression loading.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM AND RESULTS

1. Test Specimen and Compression Fixture

The specimens used in this investigation were fabricated from the unidirectional AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy tapes. Four panels with symmetrical +45/-45/0/90/0/+45/-45/0/+45/-45/0 s lay up were prepared and cured according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Delaminations were introduced by inserting Teflon films to have the effect of delamination lengths of 6.35mm, 9.53mm, 12.7mm between the second and third ply from one surface and on one side only as shown in figure 1. The specimens dimensions were modified from the normal ones [12] to allow for a wider width in order to avoid Euler's buckling in compression. These specimens were cut using a diamond head wheel to appropriate dimensions and were bonded on the ends to chemically treated aluminium tabs to give a 25.4mm gauge length, which was strain gauged on both sides and clipped gauged along one edge as shown in figure 1. The bonding material was a hot curing FM300 adhesive. Thicknesses were checked carefully before and after the bonding process to ensure the consistency of thickness distribution over each specimen. Specimens

Figure 1. Specimen geometry.

having some discrepancies in thickness distribution were faced milled along both edges to ensure no eccentricity from the midplane. Compression was applied in an Instron 1195 series via an Iitri compression jig with modified jaws to accommodate the abovementioned specimens as shown in figure 2. This jig works on the principle of shear load application through the tabs in order to achieve the required load on the specimen's testing section.

Figure 2. Compression Apparatus.

2. Compression Testing

Compression testing of composite specimens using an Iitri jig is

perhaps the most useful technique in the study of edge delamination. It allows for free ends of specimens, free and accessible testing section and eliminates any problem that is associated with clamping or end induced compressive loads. However, to acquire accurate and useful results, this technique requires a careful testing procedure which deals with the minimisation of slippage between the jig and the jaws, the jaws and the specimens and caters also for data acquisition of the deflection of the test section only. Every specimen undergoes a pre-loading cycle in order for the jaws to grip on to the specimen and eliminate any slippage. Each specimen was clipped gauged for deflection measurements. Compression loading was performed using an Instron 1195 series machine and typical results for a load deflection curve are shown in figure 4(b). Also corresponding load and strain measurements are shown in figure 3. These results were consistent throughout all tests, reproducible and have confirmed the uniformity of applied load and the success of these tests, and will be discussed later.

Figure 4(b). Instron load and deflection measurements.

3. Non Destructive Testing

A set of non destructive tests were performed to evaluate accurately the points of initiation of edge delamination. This was necessary for the critical energy release rate calculations as the load-deflection curve showed a smooth non linear behaviour. These tests included acoustic emission, ultrasonic and X-ray technique. For the acoustic emission testing the signal of a piezoelectric transducer {600 KHZ resonant frequency} was

Figure 3. Instron Load and Strain Measurements.

amplified, filtered (i.e. frequency lower than 40 KHz are filtered out) and fed to a discriminator that transformed the signal bursts into counts. This technique helped only to identify the position of initiation of delamination on the load-deflection curve. X-rays techniques were performed using a Faxtron x-rays unit where X-rays are generated for a few seconds at 15 KVP in conjunction with the use of Tetrabromoethane (TBE) (i.e. a dye penetrant opaque to X-rays). However this latter test was not successful. The delamination did not have any opening and the dye did not penetrate to the tip. This has confirmed earlier work [13] where it was observed that this lay up would not experience a Mode I behaviour but rather a closure effect and edge delamination shearing. In the ultrasonic testing a water immersion technique, using a 10 MHz damped transducer, was performed and results were more positive. This test gave a good indication of the change of position of the delamination front but failed to give its exact location to less than 0.5 mm.

Although all these tests have collectively achieved the purpose of this work in determining the initiation on the load deflection curve and verifying it, they have however demonstrated their disadvantages in locating the position of delamination initiation and delamination front of these particular specimens under the given loading conditions.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

It was observed quite clearly in every tested specimen that the load

Figure 4(a). Load Deflection Results.

deflection behaviour of edge delamination of this composite material is non-linear under the given loading conditions. Figure 4(b) is a typical load deflection curve produced on the Instron. Every instrument was retested and recalibrated to ensure the accuracy of these results. Final results for different delamination sizes are shown in figure 4(a). This curve shows also the position of delamination initiation as detected from the acoustic emission technique. Based on these observations, it becomes evident that the linear theory for calculating the critical energy release rate based on the compliance method,

$$G_C = \left(\frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \right),$$

could not be used, and that an appropriate term for G_C should be developed to cater for this behaviour.

From the fundamental theory of fracture mechanics for an incremental increase in crack size,

$$P d\delta = G_C dA + d\Lambda, \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load per unit deflection δ , G_C the critical energy release rate per unit area (dA), and $d\Lambda$ is the change of the strain energy of the system.

Thus

$$G_C = \frac{Pd\delta}{dA} - \frac{d\Lambda}{dA} \tag{2}$$

Assuming that the load deflection curve behaves according to the following relationship,

$$P = C\delta^n, \tag{3}$$

where C is a function of crack length (a). Further, if

$$\Lambda = \int_0^{\delta_C} Pd\delta, \text{ then } \Lambda = C \frac{\delta^{n+1}}{n+1},$$

and equation (2) becomes,

$$G_C = \frac{Pd\delta}{dA} - \left[\frac{\partial\Lambda}{\partial C} \frac{\partial C}{\partial A} + \frac{\partial\Lambda}{\partial\delta} \frac{\partial\delta}{\partial A} \right]. \tag{4}$$

Also,

$$\frac{\partial\Lambda}{\partial C} = \frac{\delta^{n+1}}{n+1} \text{ and } \frac{\partial\Lambda}{\partial\delta} = C\delta^n. \tag{5}$$

Substituting (5) into (4) we get,

$$G_C = \left[\frac{\delta^{n+1}}{n+1} \frac{\partial C}{\partial A} \right]_{\delta = \delta_C} \tag{6}$$

Using the information obtained in Figure 4(a) and fitting the data to equation (3), we obtain the following relationship.

$$P = C\delta^{0.78}, \tag{7}$$

where C appears to have a linear relationship with the delamination length to width ratio as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. C(vs) Crack Length.

$$C = C_D - m(a/b) \text{ where } m = 3385. \quad (8)$$

Substituting equation (8) in (6) we obtain the relationship for (G_C).

$$G_C = \frac{\delta^{n+1}}{n+1} * m/l \quad (9)$$

where l is delamination width.

From equation (9), the calculated critical energy rate for this laminate would be,

$$G_C = 2.09 \text{ N/m.}$$

This value includes the effects of all failure modes (i.e. GI, GII, GIII) and accurately represents the energy required to initiate edge delamination in these laminates under the above conditions. Although no comparison could be made here due to lack of existence of mixed mode G_C for this particular material, it would appear that this value is large in comparison to other materials mentioned in [5-6]. This could be attributed to the fact that by nature this material has strong properties, more so as the observation discussed in [13] where mode II for this particular lay-up in compression was found to be of considerable magnitude and therefore influences the overall delamination behaviour. This non-linearity is a result of the closure of the outer delaminated portions due to their asymmetric lay-up properties. The bending/membrane coupling which is dependent upon the sign of the terms in the coupling matrix can either cause outward curvature of the delaminated plies, thus enhancing the rate of delamination or can cause curvature that tries to bring the delaminated faces closer together. This latter is the essence of this analysis that led to this non-linear behaviour. The analysis of failure modes interrelationship (i.e. GI, GII, GIII) for different lay-ups would add more light on these results and would help to understand the fracture mechanics of this type of composite defect. However laminated with the above ply configuration could only be analysed using non-linear theory as the linear analysis would underestimate their critical energy release rate. This non-linear behaviour is an important observation which could have certain advantages in maintaining composite structures. Therefore it should be further studies to accommodate its features into the failure criterion for laminates under compression. Near surface edge delaminated specimens should not have a surface lay up of the form 45/-45/...etc. if delamination opening had to be investigated.

CONCLUSIONS

We have observed here that post processing using the traditional energy release rate based on the compliance method is not sufficient and that we should develop an energy release rate criterion, from the fundamental theory of fracture mechanics, that will incorporate the non-linear behaviour. The concept used may require more improvements to fully accommodate the effects of these observations. We have also indicated that the specimen preparation and the compression technique had an influence on the final results, and recommend that every effort should be implemented to accurately determine the initiation of delamination under these conditions. Surface ply orientation played an important role and should therefore be carefully chosen for the particular application.

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